

Stability Constants of Iron(III) Chelates with Some Substituted Chalcones at 0.1 M Ionic Strength and at Various Ionic Strengths of 2'-Hydroxy-4-methoxy-5'-methylchalcone

M. L. NARWADE, M. M. CHINCHOLKAR and S. W. SATHE

Department of Chemistry, Vidarbha Mahavidyalaya, Amravati-444 604

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The interaction of Fe^{III} with 2'-hydroxy-4-methoxy-5'-methylchalcone (1), 2'-hydroxy-4-methoxychalcone (2), 2'-hydroxy-3'-bromo-4-methoxy-5'-methylchalcone (3) and 2'-hydroxy-4-methoxy-5',6'-benzochalcone (4) has been investigated potentiometrically in 70% dioxane-water mixture at 0.1 M ionic strength. The study of Fe^{III} complexes with 2'-hydroxy-4-methoxy-5'-methylchalcone has also been done at 0.032, 0.052, 0.072, 0.092 and 0.112 M ionic strength.

It is observed that ferric ion forms 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 complexes with all the ligands. Proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants have been determined by Bjerrum method as adopted by Calvin and Wilson. The data of pK and log K values obtained from this technique was used to (i) verify the relation $\log K = a \text{pK} + b$, (ii) calculate the thermodynamic dissociation constants at zero ionic strength, and (iii) find the closest distance of approach between metal ion and ligand.

THE efficiency of chalcone as an analytical reagent for the spectrophotometric estimation of a number of metal cations has been recognised by Syamsunder¹. Very few complexes of chalcones have been studied employing potentiometric methods. Khadikar *et al.*²⁻⁴ have studied the chelate forming tendency of 2'-hydroxy- and 2',4'-dihydroxy-chalcones. Recently, Jaganathaswamy and Lingaiah⁵ have reported formation constants of some bivalent metal chelates of 2'-hydroxychalcone and 2'-hydroxy-5'-methylchalcone at 0.1 M ionic strength and in 70% ethanol-water mixture.

It was therefore thought of interest to study the chelating properties of other substituted chalcones under suitable conditions. In the present work the interaction of Fe^{III} with 2'-hydroxy-4-methoxy-5'-methylchalcone (1), 2'-hydroxy-4-methoxychalcone (2), 2'-hydroxy-3'-bromo-4-methoxy-5'-methylchalcone (3) and 2'-hydroxy-4-methoxy-5',6'-benzochalcone (4) has been investigated potentiometrically in 70% dioxane-water mixture at 0.1 M ionic strength.

Experimental

Ferric nitrate (B.D.H., AnalaR) was dissolved in perchloric acid and its concentration was estimated by standard procedure⁶. Since chalcones are insoluble in water, dioxane-water (70%, v/v) was used as a solvent. The other solutions were prepared in double-distilled water. 1:4-Dioxane was purified by standard method⁷ and its purity was checked by potassium iodide. pH measurements

were carried out with ELICO LI-10 pH meter (accuracy ± 0.05 unit) using glass and calomel electrodes at $27 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The B values (pH meter readings in 70% dioxane-water mixture) were converted to [H⁺] values by applying the corrections proposed by Van-Uitert and Haas⁸.

Results and Discussion

Proton-ligand stability constants: Hydroxychalcone and its substituted derivatives may be considered as monobasic acids having only one dissociable H⁺ ion from OH group and can, therefore, be represented as HL.

It is observed from titration curves that the ligand curves start deviating from the free acid (HClO₄) curves at about pH 10.0. The extent of deviation appears to depend on the nature of the substituent groups of 2'-hydroxy-4-methoxychalcone. The proton-ligand formation numbers ($\bar{\eta}_A$) were calculated by Irving and Rossotti's expression⁹. The pK values were estimated from formation curves ($\bar{\eta}_A$ vs pH) by noting the pH at which $\bar{\eta}_A = 0.5$. The accurate values of pK were determined by pointwise calculations which are presented in Table 1.

TABLE I

Chalcone (compd. l.o.)	1	2	3	4
Constant pK	11.70	11.40	11.21	6.82

It is observed from the data that pK value of ligand (4) is least and is attributed to the presence of benzene ring at 5',6'-position which acts as electron sink. The larger pK value of ligand 1 than 2 is due to electron releasing CH_3 group at 5'-position. The pK value of ligand 3 is consistent with the fact that the electron releasing tendency of 5'-methyl group overweighs that of the bromine substituent at 3'-position.

Metal-ligand stability constants: The stepwise formation constants of Fe^{III} complexes with above substituted chalcones were determined employing Bjerrum Calvin pH -titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti⁹.

The formation of chelate between Fe^{III} and different substituted chalcones was indicated by (i) the significant departure, starting at pH 2.0 of the metal complex titration curve from the ligand curve, and (ii) the change in colour from dirty brown to light brown and finally to deep brown as pH was raised from 2.0 to 6.0.

In calculating $\bar{\eta}$ and pL , the concentrations were corrected for changes in volume produced by the addition of alkali during titrations. A series of values for $\bar{\eta}$ and pL corresponding to different B values were calculated using the equation of Van-Uitert and Haas⁹.

The $\log K$ values were directly read from the formation curve ($\bar{\eta}$ vs pL) using half integral method. The most accurate values are calculated by point-wise calculations. The values of $\log K$, ($\log K_1 - \log K_2$) and $\log K_1/\log K_2$ are presented in Table 2.

One would expect a bigger difference between $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ or $\log K_2$ and $\log K_3$ values in such ligands because of possible steric hindrance to the linking of the secondary ligand to the metal ion. The smaller difference may be due to *trans* structure. The Table 2 shows that the ratio of $\log K_1/\log K_2$

TABLE 2 METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF Fe^{III} COMPLEXES WITH SUBSTITUTED CHALCONES AT 0.112 M IONIC STRENGTH

System	Constant		$\log K_1 - \log K_2$	$\frac{\log K_1}{\log K_2}$
	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$		
Fe^{III} -ligand 1	12.85	11.45	1.40	1.12
Fe^{III} -ligand 2	12.14	11.30	0.84	1.07
Fe^{III} -ligand 3	11.99	11.35	0.64	1.05
Fe^{III} -ligand 4	7.60	7.32	0.28	1.03

is positive in all cases. Separation factor between first and second formation constants are well within the expected range and the absence of high values imply that there is little or no steric hindrance to the addition of secondary ligand molecule.

Validity of $\log K = a pK + b$ relation: The linear relation $\log K = a pK + b$ has been found out by some

workers^{10,11} to hold for transition metal complexes of a series of closely related ligands. Similar plots of $\log K_1$, $\log K_2$ and $\log K_3$ against pK (Figs. 1, 2 and 3) show satisfactory linear relation giving slope values 1.10, 0.95 and 0.96, respectively. When the changes in partial molar free energies of the

Fig. 1. Plot between pK vs $\log K_1$.

Fig. 2. Plot between pK vs $\log K_2$.

Fig. 3. Plot between pK vs $\log K_3$.

metal-ligand and proton-ligand complexes exactly compensate each other, the $\log K$ vs pK plot is

linear with a slope of unity. The slope values are found to be almost unity in our present investigation.

Influence of ionic strength on complex equilibria : The stability of transition metal complexes with a great variety of ligands have been studied^{1a}. Rajan and Martell^{1a} have thoroughly investigated the interaction of uranyl and copper ions with organic ligands and correlated the stability constants of their chelates with the dissociation constants of the ligands.

The interaction of ferric metal ion with 2'-hydroxy-4-methoxy-5'-methylchalcone was undertaken with a view to study the influence of ionic strength on stability constants and to ascertain the exact mechanism of complexation equilibria. The overall ionic strength of the solution was calculated by the expression, $\mu = \frac{1}{2} \sum c_i z_i^2$. The contribution of the other ions, in addition of Na⁺ and ClO₄⁻ were also taken into consideration.

The proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants at various ionic strengths were calculated by the Irving and Rossotti's expression⁹. The accurate values of pK were calculated by pointwise calculations and are set out in Table 3. Initially

TABLE 3—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS AT VARIOUS IONIC STRENGTH IN 70% DIOXANE-WATER MIXTURE: Fe^{III}-2'-HYDROXY-4-METHOXY-5'-METHYLCHALCONE

Ionic strength	$\sqrt{\mu}$	$\frac{\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}}$	pK	log K ₁ ^a	log K ₂	log K ₃
0.032	0.1786	0.1517	11.97	13.92	13.10	12.65
0.052	0.2280	0.1857	11.91	13.65	12.85	12.30
0.072	0.2665	0.2105	11.85	13.25	12.38	11.70
0.092	0.3033	0.2328	11.75	12.92	12.00	11.95
0.112	0.3347	0.2508	11.70	12.85	11.45	10.92

log K₁ and log K₃ values were obtained by pointwise calculations, since the difference (log K₁ - log K₃) or (log K₂ - log K₃) was less than 2, their accurate values were calculated by the method of least squares. The maximum value of $\bar{\eta}$ at each ionic strength was around 3.0, which indicated that 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 complex formations are possible. It is seen from Table 3 that pK and log K values are found to decrease with increase of ionic strength. The standard deviation of these values was between 1.0 × 10⁻⁴ to 3.0 × 10⁻⁴. A representative data, i.e. of Fe^{III}-2'-hydroxy-4-methoxy-5'-methylchalcone at 0.112 M ionic strength explains adequately the precision of the experimental work (Table 4).

The Bronsted equations,

$$\log K = \log K^0 + A\Delta Z^2, \text{ and}$$

$$pK = pK^0 - A\Delta Z^2$$

were used to determine the magnitude of ΔZ^2 , where $\Delta Z^2 = [Z^2(\text{product}) - Z^2(\text{reactant})]$. The data obtained of pK and log K could be utilised to study the thermodynamic dissociation constants at zero ionic strength and to know the mechanism of

TABLE 4—STANDARD DEVIATION OF Fe^{III}-2'-HYDROXY-4-METHOXY-5'-METHYLCHALCONE AT 0.092 M IONIC STRENGTH

pH	$\bar{\eta}$ expd.	$\bar{\eta}$ calcd.	$\Delta \eta$	$\sigma = \left[\frac{\sum (\Delta \eta)^2}{n} \right]^{1/2}$
1.9	0.4228	0.4211	-0.0088	2.7 × 10 ⁻⁴
2.0	0.5100	0.5000	0.0100	
2.1	0.8280	0.8222	-0.0088	
2.2	1.0580	1.0610	-0.0030	
2.3	1.3250	1.3190	-0.0060	
2.4	1.5650	1.5770	-0.0120	
2.5	1.7020	1.7110	-0.0090	
2.6	1.8650	1.8550	0.0110	
2.7	1.9110	1.9000	0.0110	
2.8	1.2710	2.2650	0.0060	
2.9	2.3520	2.3450	0.0070	
3.0	2.5710	2.5600	0.0110	
3.1	2.8200	2.8290	0.0090	

complexation equilibria, since the complexation reactions involve ions on reactant product sites. The validity of Bronsted equation was tested for various systems by plotting the graph of pK or log K vs $\sqrt{\mu}$. The plots of pK, log K₁, log K₂ and log K₃ vs $\sqrt{\mu}$ gave straight lines. The magnitude of ΔZ^2 (Debye-Hückel constant) and slope were observed for each plot and the different possible relations are given in Table 5.

TABLE 5

Sl. no.	Reaction equilibria	Constant	ΔZ^2	
			Expected	Found
1.	HL $\rightleftharpoons$ H ⁺ + L ⁻	pK	2.00	1.95
2.	HL + Fe ³⁺ $\rightleftharpoons$ H ⁺ + FeL ²⁺	log K ₁	-4.00	17.50
3.	HL + FeL ²⁺ $\rightleftharpoons$ H ⁺ + FeL ₂ ⁺	log K ₂	-2.00	12.50
4.	HL + FeL ₂ ⁺ $\rightleftharpoons$ H ⁺ + FeL ₃	log K ₃	0.00	22.84

There is a good agreement of ΔZ^2 between expected and observed values for reaction (1), but the observed values of ΔZ^2 in remaining relations are more than those expected. The same discrepancy was also recorded by Narwade and Sathe¹⁴. The plots of pK/log K vs $\sqrt{\mu}(1 + \sqrt{\mu})$ and $\sqrt{\mu}/(1 + \sqrt{\mu}) - 0.3\sqrt{\mu}$ also gave the linearship without any improvement in the magnitude of ΔZ^2 . The discrepancy may be due to the fact that the value for "a" (closest distance approach) was fixed at 3.3 Å. It was, therefore, decided to calculate "a" value in order to understand the discrepancy.

Calculation of accurate "a" value : The most accurate value of "a" can be calculated by method of successive approximations by substituting different values of "a" in Bronsted and Christiansen's equation¹⁵,

$$\log K = \log K^0 + \frac{A\Delta Z^2 \sqrt{\mu}}{1 + Ba \sqrt{\mu}}$$

and observing its influence on log K⁰ vs $\sqrt{\mu}$ plots. It is expected that for the correct value of "a", log K vs $\sqrt{\mu}$ plot should be linear and parallel to

the $\sqrt{\mu}$ axis. The calculations were made by taking the values of A and B in 70% dioxane-water mixture at 27° taken from the work of Harned and Owen¹⁶.

None of the plots (except "a" = 5.0 Å) is parallel to the $\sqrt{\mu}$ axis. It may, therefore, be concluded that the value of "a" for Fe^{III}-2'-hydroxy-4-methoxy-5'-methylchalcone 1:1 complex in 70% dioxane-water mixture is 5.0 Å. The thermodynamic values of stability constants observed from various plots at zero ionic strength are presented in Table 6.

TABLE 6—THERMODYNAMIC STABILITY CONSTANTS AT ZERO IONIC STRENGTH

System	Plot	pK° or lg K°
2'-Hydroxy-4-methoxy- 5'-methylchalcone	$pK \text{ vs } \sqrt{\mu}$	12.30
	$pK \text{ vs } \sqrt{\mu}/(1 + \sqrt{\mu})$	12.35
	$pK \text{ vs } [\sqrt{\mu}/(1 + \sqrt{\mu}) - 0.3\sqrt{\mu}]$	12.30
Fe ^{III} -2'-hydroxy-4- methoxy-5'-methyl- chalcone	$\log K_1 \text{ vs } \sqrt{\mu}$	15.60
	$\log K_1 \text{ vs } \sqrt{\mu}/(1 + \sqrt{\mu})$	15.55
	$\log K_1 \text{ vs } [\sqrt{\mu}/(1 + \sqrt{\mu}) - 0.3\sqrt{\mu}]$	15.65
-do-	$\log K_2 \text{ vs } \sqrt{\mu}$	15.10
	$\log K_2 \text{ vs } \sqrt{\mu}/(1 + \sqrt{\mu})$	15.15
	$\log K_2 \text{ vs } [\sqrt{\mu}/(1 + \sqrt{\mu}) - 0.3\sqrt{\mu}]$	15.00
-do-	$\log K_3 \text{ vs } \sqrt{\mu}$	14.95
	$\log K_3 \text{ vs } \sqrt{\mu}/(1 + \sqrt{\mu})$	14.97
	$\log K_3 \text{ vs } [\sqrt{\mu}/(1 + \sqrt{\mu}) - 0.3\sqrt{\mu}]$	14.90

It can be seen that there is a good agreement among thermodynamic constants obtained from various plots.

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